

Computer-Aided Uncertainty Modeling of Nonlinear Parameter-Dependent Systems, Part I: Theoretical Overview

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Abstract

Robust control system analysis and design is based on an uncertainty description, called a linear fractional transformation (LFT), which separates uncertainties from the nominal system model. These models include both parametric and non-parametric uncertainties for many practical problems. LFT formulation for these "mixed uncertainty" systems involves formulation of a linear parameter varying (LPV) model, construction of a low-order parametric LFT model, and validation of a mixed uncertainty model with respect to measurement data. This paper provides an overview of uncertainty modeling methods and software tools being developed for application to mixed uncertainty systems. These methods and tools provide a computer-aided uncertainty modeling capability that makes current robust and LPV control methods accessible to a broad class of practical problems.

1. Introduction

Robust control theory makes possible the analysis and design of multivariable control systems for robustness to explicitly defined system uncertainties. A block diagram of the system model is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Robust Control System Block Diagram

Block matrix P (partitioned as P_{11} , P_{12} , P_{21} , and P_{22}) represents the generalized nominal plant, Δ is an uncertainty matrix, x is the state vector, u is the control input vector, and y is a vector of measurement signals. Signals w_Δ and z_Δ provide the connections between Δ and P. Systems whose models contain both parametric and non-parametric uncertainties will be referred to in this paper as "mixed uncertainty" systems.

The separated system description of the nominal part, P, and the uncertain part, Δ , is referred to as a P- Δ model and falls within a broader class of system descriptions generally referred to as a linear fractional transformation (LFT). The uncertainty block, Δ , for mixed uncertainty systems represents both parametric and non-parametric uncertainties, and can therefore contain real scalar

parameters and complex blocks. The uncertainty structure addressed in this paper is defined as follows,

$$\Delta = \text{diag} [\Delta(\delta), \Delta_c] \quad (1.1)$$

$$\Delta(\delta) = \text{diag} [\delta_1 I_{n_1}, \delta_2 I_{n_2}, \dots, \delta_m I_{n_m}] \quad (1.2a)$$

$$\dim[\Delta(\delta)] = n_\Delta = \sum_{i=1}^m n_i \quad (1.2b)$$

$$\delta = [\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_m] \in \mathbb{R}^m \quad (1.3)$$

$$\Delta_c = \text{diag} [\Delta_1(s), \Delta_2(s), \dots, \Delta_{m_c}(s)] \quad (1.4)$$

where m and m_c denote the number of parameters and complex uncertainty blocks in the model.

For robust control problems, the formulation of a P- Δ model that accurately characterizes system uncertainties is important, since robustness results depend directly on the uncertainty model used in the analysis / design. Moreover, nominal performance is being traded for robustness in designing a robust control system. LFT uncertainty models can also be utilized in the application of linear parameter varying (LPV) control methods (Ref. [1]) for designing parameter-dependent control systems that function over the operational envelope of the nonlinear system. LPV control methods do not require that the system model be represented in LFT form. However, the use of an LFT model allows LPV control to be combined with μ -Synthesis (Ref. [2]) to design robust parameter-dependent control systems that provide robustness to non-scheduled parametric uncertainties and unmodeled dynamics.

The process for formulating and validating accurate P- Δ models for practical problems can be very complicated, especially for systems with nonlinear parameter dependencies. While some research has been performed and published on uncertainty modeling (e.g., Refs. [3]-[14] and their references), there are currently no commercially available software tools which provide a computer aided uncertainty modeling capability to the controls practitioner. This paper summarizes an uncertainty modeling process to construct LFT models for nonlinear mixed uncertainty systems that can be used for robust control system analysis and design and for LPV control. Section 2 summarizes a method for constructing an LPV model, Section 3 presents a numerical approach for computing an equivalent low-order parametric LFT model, and Section 4 presents a method for obtaining a validated mixed uncertainty model for the system. Some concluding remarks are given in Section 5. An example problem using the methods presented in this paper is provided in Ref. [15].

2. LPV Model Formulation

A nonlinear system or simulation can be used to generate data over the independent parameter space being considered in the development of an LPV model. A method for parameterizing the data using multivariate polynomial functions of the independent (varying) parameters is the subject of Ref. [16]. This method is based on orthogonal function modeling and utilizes a predicted squared error metric to determine the fewest number of functions required to adequately fit the data in a least squares sense. The parameterized models are then used in constructing an LPV model of the system. An overview of the orthogonal function modeling technique is given below.

2.1 Orthogonal Function Modeling

Assume an N -dimensional vector of dependent variable values, $\mathbf{y} = [y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N]^T$, modeled in terms of a linear combination of n modeling functions $p_j, j=1,2,\dots,n$. Each p_j is an N -dimensional vector, which in general depends on the independent variables. Then,

$$\mathbf{y} = a_1 p_1 + a_2 p_2 + \dots + a_n p_n + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (2.1)$$

The $a_j, j=1,2,\dots,n$ are constant model parameters and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ denotes the modeling error vector. We put aside for the moment the question of how to determine the modeling functions p_j , as well as how to select which functions should be included in the model of Eq. (2.1) (which implicitly determines n). Now define an $N \times n$ matrix P ,

$$P = [p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n] \quad (2.2)$$

and let $\mathbf{a} = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n]^T$. Eq. (2.1) can be written as:

$$\mathbf{y} = P\mathbf{a} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (2.3)$$

The goal is to determine \mathbf{a} that minimizes the least squares cost function

$$J = (\mathbf{y} - P\mathbf{a})^T (\mathbf{y} - P\mathbf{a}) = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (2.4)$$

The least squares estimate of \mathbf{a} is

$$\hat{\mathbf{a}} = [P^T P]^{-1} P^T \mathbf{y} \quad (2.5)$$

and the estimated parameter covariance matrix is (see Ref. [16])

$$\text{var}(\hat{\mathbf{a}}) = E\{(\hat{\mathbf{a}} - \mathbf{a})(\hat{\mathbf{a}} - \mathbf{a})^T\} = \frac{\hat{J}}{(N-n)} [P^T P]^{-1} \quad (2.6)$$

where E is the expectation operator, and \hat{J} is the cost calculated from Eq. (2.4) with $\mathbf{a} = \hat{\mathbf{a}}$. Estimated model output is

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}} = P\hat{\mathbf{a}} \quad (2.7)$$

Ref. [16] describes a procedure for using the independent variable data to generate orthogonal modeling functions, which have the following important property:

$$p_i^T p_j = 0, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (2.8)$$

Using Eqs. (2.2) and (2.8) in Eq. (2.5), the j th element of the estimated parameter vector $\hat{\mathbf{a}}$ is given by

$$\hat{a}_j = \frac{(p_j^T \mathbf{y})}{(p_j^T p_j)} \quad (2.9)$$

Combining Eqs. (2.2), (2.4), and (2.7)-(2.9), yields

$$\hat{J} = \mathbf{y}^T \mathbf{y} - \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{(p_j^T \mathbf{y})^2}{(p_j^T p_j)} \quad (2.10)$$

Eq. (2.10) shows that when the modeling functions are orthogonal, the reduction in the estimated cost resulting from including the term $a_j p_j$ in the model depends only on the dependent variable data \mathbf{y} and the added orthogonal modeling function p_j . This decouples the least squares estimation, and makes it possible to evaluate each orthogonal modeling function in terms of its ability to reduce the least squares model fit to the data, regardless of which other orthogonal modeling functions are present in the model. The orthogonal modeling functions are chosen to minimize predicted squared error (PSE), defined (see Ref. [17])

$$\text{PSE} = \frac{\hat{J}}{N} + \sigma_0^2 \frac{n}{N} \quad (2.11)$$

where

$$\sigma_0^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2, \bar{y} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N y_i \quad (2.12)$$

In Eq. (2.11), the PSE depends on the mean square fit error \hat{J}/N , and a term proportional to the number of terms in the model, n . The latter term prevents overfitting to too many model terms, which is detrimental to model prediction accuracy (see Ref. [17]). Note that while the mean square fit error \hat{J}/N must decrease with the addition of each orthogonal modeling function by Eq. (2.10), the overfit penalty term $\sigma_0^2 n/N$ increases with each added model term (n increases), so that PSE always has a single global minimum value. Ref. [17] contains details on the statistical properties of the PSE metric, including justification for its use in modeling problems.

The orthogonal functions are generated in a manner that allows them to be decomposed without ambiguity into an expansion of ordinary multivariate polynomials. The process can be repeated to generate orthogonal functions of arbitrary order in the independent variables, subject only to limitations related to the information contained in the data.

Using orthogonal functions to model the dependent variable makes it possible to evaluate the merit of including each modeling function individually as part of the model, using the predicted squared error, PSE. This approach makes model structure determination a well-defined and

straightforward process. After the orthogonal modeling functions that minimize PSE are selected, each retained orthogonal function is expanded into an ordinary polynomial expression, and common terms in the ordinary polynomials are combined using double precision arithmetic to arrive finally at a multivariate model using only ordinary polynomials in the independent variables. Ordinary polynomial terms that contribute less than 0.1 percent of the final model rms magnitude are dropped.

Orthogonal modeling functions are useful in determining the model structure for the dependent variable using the *PSE* metric, by virtue of the benefits of orthogonal functions and the resultant decoupling of the associated least squares problem. The subsequent decomposition of the retained orthogonal functions is done to express the results in physically meaningful terms and to allow analytic differentiation for partial derivatives of the dependent variable with respect to the independent variables.

2.2 Construction of the LPV Model

Several approaches can be used to formulate an LPV model based on the parameterization method of Section 2.1. One approach is to parameterize the matrix elements associated with a set of linear models generated over the parameter space. Another approach is to parameterize the underlying physical parameters of a linear model of the system. A third approach is to parameterize the physical parameters of the nonlinear system model, and then linearize the system at an equilibrium point while retaining the variable parameters of interest. Ref. [18] presents a linearization technique that allows the determination of equilibrium surfaces and the formulation of LPV models at or near bifurcation points.

The resulting LPV model can then be represented by the following compact state space equation.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A(\delta) & B(\delta) \\ C(\delta) & D(\delta) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ u \end{bmatrix} = S(\delta) \begin{bmatrix} x \\ u \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.13)$$

A more general LPV model can also be obtained to allow the direct representation of rational problems in a multivariate polynomial form. For example, multivariate polynomial models can be obtained for the generalized state space system model

$$\begin{aligned} E(\delta) \dot{x} &= A(\delta) x + B(\delta) u ; y = C(\delta) x + D(\delta) u \\ \Rightarrow \dot{x} &= [E(\delta)]^{-1} A(\delta) x + [E(\delta)]^{-1} B(\delta) u \\ y &= C(\delta) x + D(\delta) u \end{aligned}$$

where elements in A, B, C, D, and E have been parameterized. This system model can then be represented in compact form as follows.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} E(\delta) & 0 \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} A(\delta) & B(\delta) \\ C(\delta) & D(\delta) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ u \end{bmatrix} = \tilde{S}_D^{-1} \tilde{S}_N \begin{bmatrix} x \\ u \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.14)$$

Using this parameterization approach, an LFT model can be obtained using multivariate polynomial methods even though the problem has a rational form. This is discussed further in Section 3.1, and in greater detail in Ref. [6].

The δ_i parameters in the above equations represent the independent uncertain or varying parameters of the system.

In standard P- Δ model form, each δ_i parameter is normalized. Scaling associated with the parameterization process and for normalizing the uncertain parameters can be accomplished as a separate step once the LFT model structure has been obtained. This is discussed in Ref. [6].

3. Parametric LFT Model Computation

Transformation of the LPV model into LFT form involves the formulation of the LFT problem to be solved, and the computation of an LFT model solution. The LFT representation of the LPV model is exact, and should be of the lowest possible dimension. The general problem is to find a separated state-space uncertainty model in the LFT form, as defined by Figure 1. The state-space parametric LFT model equations are given below

$$z_\Delta = P_{11} w_\Delta + P_{12} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ u \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.1a)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ y \end{bmatrix} = P_{21} w_\Delta + P_{22} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ u \end{bmatrix}, w_\Delta = \Delta z_\Delta \quad (3.1b)$$

where Δ is given by Eqn. (1.2). Note that finding a solution for P_{11} , P_{12} , P_{21} , and P_{22} such that the resulting uncertainty model is low-order means that n_Δ in Eqn. (1.2b) should be as small as possible. This is equivalent to requiring that the total number of repetitions from each parameter be as small as possible.

3.1 Parametric LFT Problem Formulation

In order to obtain an LFT model of the LPV system, an LFT problem must first be formed. Closing the Δ -loop in Figure 1 using Eqns. (3.1) yields the following equation.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \left\{ P_{21} \Delta (I - P_{11} \Delta)^{-1} P_{12} + P_{22} \right\} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ u \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.2)$$

Comparing Eqns. (2.13) and (3.2), the following LFT equation for $S(\delta)$ can be obtained.

$$S(\delta) = P_{21} (I - \Delta P_{11})^{-1} \Delta P_{12} + P_{22} \quad (3.3)$$

$$\Rightarrow S(\delta) = S_\Delta(\delta) + S_0 \quad (3.4)$$

Thus, $S(\delta)$ contains a nominal component and an uncertain component that depends on Δ , as defined by the following equations.

$$S_0 = \begin{bmatrix} A_0 & B_0 \\ C_0 & D_0 \end{bmatrix} = P_{22} \quad (3.5)$$

$$S_{\Delta}(\delta) = P_{21}(I - \Delta P_{11})^{-1} \Delta P_{12} \quad (3.6)$$

Since P_{22} is easily determined from the nominal system model, formulation of the LFT problem consists of forming Eqn. (3.6) from the system model of Eqn. (2.13). If the elements of the A, B, C, and D matrices of Eqn. (2.13) are multivariate polynomial functions of δ , the nominal and uncertain parts of the system can be easily separated as follows.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ y \end{bmatrix} = S(\delta) \begin{bmatrix} x \\ u \end{bmatrix} = \{S_o + S_{\Delta}(\delta)\} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ u \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.7a)$$

$$S_{\Delta}(\delta) = \begin{bmatrix} A_{\Delta}(\delta) & B_{\Delta}(\delta) \\ C_{\Delta}(\delta) & D_{\Delta}(\delta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.7b)$$

Then Eqn. (3.7) can be directly rewritten in the form of Eqns. (3.1) by defining an input vector, w_{Δ} , and an output vector, z_{Δ} , associated with the uncertain part of the system.

If the elements of the system A, B, C, and D matrices given in Eqn. (2.13) are rational functions of δ , the expansion of Eqn. (3.7) cannot be performed directly. For this case, a matrix fraction description (MFD) of the system model, $S(\delta)$, must first be obtained in order to decompose the system into numerator and denominator matrices, as shown below for right (R) and left (L) MFD's.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ y \end{bmatrix} = S(\delta) \begin{bmatrix} x \\ u \end{bmatrix} = S_N S_D^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ u \end{bmatrix} = \tilde{S}_D^{-1} \tilde{S}_N \begin{bmatrix} x \\ u \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.8a)$$

$$S_{\Delta_R}(\delta) = \begin{bmatrix} S_{\Delta_N} \\ S_{\Delta_D} \end{bmatrix}; S_{\Delta_L}(\delta) = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{S}_{\Delta_N} & \tilde{S}_{\Delta_D} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.8b)$$

Additional details associated with formulating the LFT modeling problem for the rational case are given in Ref. [6]. Alternatively, the generalized LPV model of Eqn. (2.14) can be directly obtained for rational problems by parameterizing the A, B, C, D, and E matrices. Once Eqn. (2.14) is formed either directly or through an MFD, a single $S_{\Delta}(\delta)$ matrix can be obtained as follows.

$$S_{\Delta}(\delta) = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{S}_{N_{\Delta}} & \tilde{S}_{D_{\Delta}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{\Delta} & B_{\Delta} & E_{\Delta} & 0 \\ C_{\Delta} & D_{\Delta} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.9)$$

Using this formulation, uncertainties appearing in E can be modeled directly without having to perform the indicated inversion and multiplication. This clearly simplifies the uncertainty modeling process. Other decompositions can be similarly performed.

3.2 Parametric LFT Model Construction

Once Eqn. (3.6) and the corresponding $S_{\Delta}(\delta)$ matrix have been formed for the uncertain system, an LFT model can be obtained. Constructing the LFT model consists of solving Eqn. (3.6) for P_{21} , P_{12} , and P_{11} such that the

dimension of the Δ matrix (as defined by Eqn. (1.2)) is as small as possible, and determining P_{22} from the nominal system matrices as given in Eqn. (3.5). This is equivalent to a multidimensional minimal realization problem for which no general theory has been developed. See Ref. [19] for a discussion of multidimensional systems theory.

A numerical method to compute an LFT model for multivariate polynomial problems is presented in Refs. [7] and [10]. Note that this method can be applied to solve rational parameter problems using the LFT problem formulation described briefly above and in more detail in Ref. [6]. An overview of the numerical LFT modeling approach of Refs. [7] and [10] is given below.

Equation (3.6) can be solved for multivariate polynomial problems by replacing the matrix inversion with a finite series expansion and a nilpotency condition,

$$S_{\Delta}(\delta) = P_{21} \Delta P_{12} + P_{21} [\Delta P_{11} + (\Delta P_{11})^2 + \dots + (\Delta P_{11})^r] \Delta P_{12} \quad (3.10)$$

$$(\Delta P_{11})^{r+1} = 0 \quad (3.11)$$

where r is determined by the degree of the largest nonzero term in $S_{\Delta}(\delta)$. In order to solve Eqns. (3.10) and (3.11), an expanded definition of P_{11} , P_{12} , and P_{21} containing partitioned submatrices associated with the $\delta_i I_{n_i}$ blocks of Δ given in Eqn. (1.2) are defined for $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

$$P_{21} = [P_{21_{\delta_i}}]^T; P_{11} = [P_{11_{\delta_i \delta_j}}]; P_{12} = [P_{12_{\delta_j}}] \quad (3.12)$$

where: $P_{11_{\delta_i \delta_j}} \in R^{n_i \times n_j}$,

$$P_{12_{\delta_i}} \in R^{n_i \times n_{\text{cols}}}, P_{21_{\delta_i}} \in R^{n_{\text{rows}} \times n_i} \quad (3.13)$$

and each P_{11} main-diagonal block is nilpotent of index η_i :

$$(P_{11_{\delta_i \delta_i}})^{\eta_i} = 0, \quad \eta_i \leq n_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (3.14a)$$

$$\eta_i = \deg_{\max}(\delta_i) \quad (3.14b)$$

From Eqn. (3.12), P_{21} is a partitioned block-row matrix, P_{11} is a partitioned square matrix, and P_{12} is a partitioned block-column matrix. The uncertainty modeling problem requires that Eqn. (3.10) be solved for P_{21} , P_{12} , P_{11} , and $\Delta(\delta)$ such that the nilpotency condition of Eqn. (3.11) is satisfied. In order to satisfy this nilpotency condition, the matrix P_{11} must itself be nilpotent (to satisfy the case when $\Delta = I$). Allowing P_{11} to have a pre-defined nilpotent structure provides a means of somewhat simplifying the solution. It is shown in Ref. [10] that block triangular matrices with nilpotent main-diagonal blocks are nilpotent. The block-triangular structure is sufficient but not necessary for nilpotency, and other special structures can also be found. Solution of Eqn. (3.10) for the matrices P_{21} , P_{12} , P_{11} and $\Delta(\delta)$ can then be reduced to solving the following set of equations (Ref. [10]).

Linear δ_i Terms:

$$P_{21\delta_i} P_{12\delta_i} = S_{\Delta_0\delta_i}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (3.15)$$

ξ^{th} -Degree δ_i Terms:

$$P_{21\delta_i} (P_{11\delta_i\delta_i})^{\xi-1} P_{12\delta_i} = S_{\Delta_{\delta-1}(\delta_i)^\xi}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m; \quad \xi = 1, 2, \dots, \eta_i \quad (3.16)$$

Crossterms:

$$\begin{aligned} & P_{21\delta_{i_1}} (P_{11\delta_{i_1}\delta_{i_1}})^{\xi_{i_1}-1} P_{11\delta_{i_1}\delta_{i_2}} (P_{11\delta_{i_2}\delta_{i_2}})^{\xi_{i_2}-1} \\ & \dots P_{11\delta_{i_{n_T-1}}\delta_{i_{n_T}}} (P_{11\delta_{i_{n_T}}\delta_{i_{n_T}}})^{\xi_{i_{n_T}}-1} P_{12\delta_{i_{n_T}}} \\ & = S_{\Delta_{\xi-1}(\delta_{i_1})^{\xi_{i_1}} (\delta_{i_2})^{\xi_{i_2}} \dots (\delta_{i_{n_T}})^{\xi_{i_{n_T}}}} \quad (3.17) \end{aligned}$$

where: $\xi = \xi_{i_1} + \xi_{i_2} + \dots + \xi_{i_{n_T}}$
 $i_1 = 1, 2, \dots, m - (n_T - 1)$
 $i_2 = i_1 + 1, i_1 + 2, \dots, m - (n_T - 2)$
 \vdots
 $i_{n_T} = i_1 + (n_T - 1), \dots, m$

$n_T =$ number of parameters in the crossterm $\leq m$

Note that the S_Δ terms on the right-hand side of Eqns. (3.15) through (3.17) are the known constant matrix coefficients associated with the indicated parameter terms in $S_\Delta(\delta)$. Moreover, depending on the number of parameters and the degree of each appearing in $S_\Delta(\delta)$, there can be literally hundreds of S_Δ coefficient terms and coupled matrix equations to be solved (or more).

3.2.1 Solution of P_{21} , P_{12} , and Main-Diagonal Blocks of P_{11}

The blocks of P_{21} and P_{12} , and the main-diagonal blocks of P_{11} are solved simultaneously for each uncertain parameter δ_i using the linear and ξ^{th} -degree δ_i terms defined by Eqns. (3.15) and (3.16). The solution is accomplished such that the resulting main-diagonal blocks of P_{11} are nilpotent with the appropriate index of nilpotency, as required by Eqn. (3.14). This solution is accomplished numerically with a matrix singular value decomposition (svd) by recognizing that this part of the problem is equivalent to a 1-D state-space (minimal) realization problem and by appropriately defining the equivalent block Hankel matrices. The solution is

accomplished for each δ_i parameter as shown by the following theorem (based on Theorem 6-4, pages 268 - 272, of Ref. [20]).

Theorem 3.1

Consider the linear and ξ^{th} -degree δ_i terms of $S_\Delta(\delta)$, which can be expanded as follows

$$S_{\Delta_{L,\zeta}}(\delta) = [S_{\Delta_0\delta_i}] \delta_i + [S_{\Delta_{1\delta_i^2}}] \delta_i^2 + \dots + [S_{\Delta_{\eta_i-1\delta_i^{\eta_i}}}] \delta_i^{\eta_i} \quad (3.18a)$$

$$\Rightarrow S_{\Delta_{L,\zeta}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\eta_i} [S_{\Delta_{n-1\delta_i^n}}] \delta_i^n \quad (3.18b)$$

and use the constant coefficient matrices of Eqn. (3.18) to form the block Hankel matrices defined below

$$\bar{S}_{\Delta_0\delta_i} = \text{Hankel}[S_{\Delta_0\delta_i} \quad S_{\Delta_{1\delta_i^2}} \quad \dots \quad S_{\Delta_{\eta_i-1\delta_i^{\eta_i}}}] \quad (3.19)$$

$$\bar{S}_{\Delta_1\delta_i} = \text{Hankel}[S_{\Delta_{1\delta_i^2}} \quad \dots \quad S_{\Delta_{\eta_i-1\delta_i^{\eta_i}}} \quad 0] \quad (3.20)$$

where:

$$\text{Hankel}\begin{bmatrix} H_1 & H_2 & \dots & H_n \\ H_2 & \dots & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \dots & \dots & \vdots \\ H_n & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.21)$$

Eqn. (3.20) can be constructed from (3.19) by shifting each block row up and filling in the bottom block row with zero blocks. Define the matrix svd of Eqn. (3.19) as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{S}_{\Delta_0\delta_i} &= U_{\delta_i} \Sigma_{\delta_i} V_{\delta_i}^T = (U_{\delta_i} \Sigma_{\delta_i}^{1/2}) (\Sigma_{\delta_i}^{1/2} V_{\delta_i}^T) \\ &= \bar{P}_{21\delta_i} \bar{P}_{12\delta_i} \quad (3.22) \end{aligned}$$

where: $\text{rank}(\bar{S}_{\Delta_0\delta_i}) = \text{rank}(\bar{P}_{21\delta_i}) = \text{rank}(\bar{P}_{12\delta_i})$

Then, $\{P_{11\delta_i\delta_i}, P_{12\delta_i}\}$ is controllable and $\{P_{21\delta_i}, P_{11\delta_i\delta_i}\}$ is observable, and the matrices $P_{21\delta_i}$, $P_{12\delta_i}$, and $P_{11\delta_i\delta_i}$ form an

irreducible realization of $S_{\Delta_{L,\zeta}}(\delta)$ as defined by Eqn. (3.18), where:

$$P_{21\delta_i} = \begin{bmatrix} I_{n_{\text{rows}}} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \bar{P}_{21\delta_i} \quad (3.23)$$

$$P_{12\delta_i} = \bar{P}_{12\delta_i} \begin{bmatrix} I_{n_{\text{cols}}} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.24)$$

$$P_{11_{\delta_i \delta_i}} = (\bar{P}_{21_{\delta_i}})^{\dagger} \bar{S}_{\Delta_{\delta_i}} (\bar{P}_{12_{\delta_i}})^{\dagger} \quad (3.25)$$

and the notation $(A)^{\dagger}$ designates the pseudoinverse of matrix A . Moreover, the $P_{11_{\delta_i \delta_i}}$ matrix is nilpotent with index η_i . \parallel

Proof: See Ref. [10]

3.2.2 Solution of P_{11} Off-Diagonal Blocks

The P_{11} off-diagonal blocks are each solved using the appropriate crossterms of $S_{\Delta}(\delta)$, as defined by Eqn. (3.17). The equation to be solved for each off-diagonal block of P_{11} is a generalized linear matrix equation. This equation is given below for computing $P_{11_{\delta_n \delta_j}}$, where $n = 1, 2, \dots, m-1$ and $j = n+1, n+2, \dots, m$.

$$(\bar{P}_{21_{\delta_n}} \quad [n] \bar{P}_{11_{\delta_n}} \quad [n]) P_{11_{\delta_n \delta_j}} (\bar{P}_{12_{\delta_j}})^{\dagger} = \bar{S}_{\Delta_{\delta_n}} \quad [n] \quad (3.26)$$

The matrices $\bar{P}_{21_{\delta_n}} \quad [n]$, $\bar{P}_{11_{\delta_n}} \quad [n]$, $\bar{P}_{12_{\delta_j}} \quad [n]$, and $\bar{S}_{\Delta_{\delta_n}} \quad [n]$ in Eqn. (3.26) are comprised of known matrices as well as matrices that have already been computed at this point in the solution process. Their explicit general definition is lengthy and has therefore been omitted here for brevity (see Ref. [10]).

The general equation for computing each P_{11} off-diagonal block, $P_{11_{\delta_n \delta_j}}$ given by Eqn. (3.26) can be written as a generalized linear matrix equation

$$AXB = C \quad (3.27)$$

where A , B , and C are known constant matrices. Thus, solution of the off-diagonal blocks of P_{11} can be reduced to solving matrix equations of the form of Eqn. (3.27), which requires satisfaction of the following rank conditions.

$$\text{rank} [A \ C] = \text{rank} [A] \quad , \quad \text{rank} [B^T \ C^T]^T = \text{rank} [B]$$

Refs. [7] and [10] contain additional details on obtaining this solution.

3.2.3 Full P - Δ Model Solution

Once the $P_{21_{\delta_i}}$, $P_{12_{\delta_i}}$, $P_{11_{\delta_i \delta_i}}$, and $P_{11_{\delta_i \delta_j}}$ matrices for each parameter have been determined, the full solution is assembled using Eqns. (3.8) - (3.13). This is a simple matter of collecting the matrix partitions together into the full P_{21} , P_{12} , and P_{11} matrices. The Δ matrix is also known and given by Eqn. (1.2), where the number of repetitions for each parameter, η_i , was determined in solving the $P_{21_{\delta_i}}$, $P_{12_{\delta_i}}$, $P_{11_{\delta_i \delta_i}}$, and $P_{11_{\delta_i \delta_j}}$ matrices.

4. Formulation of a Validated Mixed Uncertainty Model

The parametric LFT model derived in Sections 2 and 3 is not a complete characterization of the uncertainties associated with the actual system. This can be attributed to fit errors in the parameters in trying to limit the order of the parameterized model, unmodeled dynamics, and other unmodeled characteristics. Therefore, as a final step in the uncertainty modeling process, the discrepancy between the parametric LFT model and the actual system is addressed by introducing uncertainties for the unmodeled dynamics and a small parameter uncertainty allowance over the uncertain parameter space to account for the inexactness of the parametric LFT model. This is accomplished by defining an additional LFT structure and using system input and output time histories to identify the uncertainty bounds associated with the augmented (mixed) LFT model. This technique can also be used for LFT model validation. A more detailed description of this process is given in Ref. [14], and a brief overview is given below.

4.1 Identification Framework

A block diagram representation of the system and the uncertainty bound identification framework is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Block Diagrams for Uncertainty Bound Identification

Given a linearized and approximately time-invariant plant, P , about an operating point, suppose a controller, K , is

known to be internally stabilizing and its command inputs, r , and outputs, y , can be measured. The exogenous inputs consist of measurement noise and disturbances either through the control input channel or through a separate path. To model this, a noise filter, V , and a disturbance filter imbedded in the augmented nominal plant, P , are assumed. Both filters are assumed driven by unknown but bounded independent random signals. The closed-loop output of the plant model, \tilde{y} , is a sum of responses due to filtered noise, v , and disturbances, ε , known input signal, r , all subject to feedback between a known controller, K , and a plant which belongs to a set defined by an upper LFT model,

$$F_u(P, \Delta) = [P_{22}, P_{23}] + P_{21} \Delta (I - P_{11} \Delta)^{-1} [P_{12}, P_{13}]$$

where the structured uncertainty is defined by $\Delta \in D$, with

$$D = \{\Delta \in C^{m \times n} : \Delta = \text{diag}[\delta_1 I_{n_1}, \delta_2 I_{n_2}, \dots, \delta_m I_{n_m}], (4.1)$$

$$\Delta_{m+1}(s), \Delta_2(s), \dots, \Delta_\tau(s), \delta_i \in F_i, \Delta_i \in C^{m_i \times n_i}\} (4.2)$$

and τ denotes the total number of uncertainty blocks.

For convenience, combine both exogenous disturbances ε and v into a single disturbance vector, β (see Figure 2). For an open-loop problem, $G(P, K, V) = G(P, 0, V)$, $r = u$, and all the remaining developments remain the same. Assume that the measurements are taken in the discrete-time domain and consider a discrete frequency-domain formulation, where we assume that a discrete Fourier transform has been performed with appropriate windowing and averaging to properly condition the truncated raw discrete-time signals.

Definition: Model Validation

Given measurements of the input signal, r , output signal, y , a noise filter, V , an augmented nominal plant model, P , a disturbance filter imbedded in P , a controller, K , and a matrix of structured uncertainty norms,

$$W = \text{diag}[\omega_1 I_{n_1}, \omega_2 I_{n_2}, \dots, \omega_m I_{n_m}]$$

the set of plants (robust control design model)

$$D_W = \{\Delta \in D : \Delta = \Delta_B W, \bar{\sigma}(\Delta_B) \leq 1\}$$

is said to be a model validating set (or at least not invalidated by available measurement data) if it contains an uncertainty model $\Delta \in D_W$ such that there exists exogenous disturbance signals, ε , v with $\|\varepsilon\| \leq 1$, $\|v\| \leq 1$ for which

$$y = F_u(G(P, K, V), \Delta) \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon \\ v \\ r \end{bmatrix}$$

4.2 Identification of Model Validating Sets

In this section, we outline a way to effectively parameterize all model validating uncertainty sets which

satisfy a priori assumptions on the LFT structure and exogenous disturbances. There exists an uncertainty signal, ξ , a disturbance ε to the plant model, and an output noise signal v for which β is norm bounded by 1 and such that,

$$e_y^o = y - G_{23}r = G_{21}\xi + G_{22}\beta (4.4)$$

iff the following conditions hold (Constant Matrix Test):

$$e_y^o \in \text{Im}(M), \quad M = [G_{21}, G_{22}] (4.5)$$

$$\|T_2^H(M^+)_\beta e_y^o\| \leq 1 (4.6)$$

where

$$(N_M)_\beta = \begin{bmatrix} T_1 & T_2 \\ \Sigma_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_1^H \\ U_2^H \end{bmatrix} (4.7)$$

If conditions (4.5) and (4.6) are satisfied, then all such triples (ξ, ε, v) are given by the parameterization

$$\begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \xi_o \\ \beta_o \end{bmatrix} + \Omega \begin{bmatrix} \phi \\ \psi \end{bmatrix} (4.8)$$

where

$$\Omega = N_M U \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_1^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & I_\Omega \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \xi_o \\ \beta_o \end{bmatrix} = [M^+ - N_M((N_M)_\beta)^+ (M^+)_\beta] e_y^o$$

and where $\psi \in C^n$ is arbitrary, and $\phi \in C^n$ satisfies

$$\|\phi\| \leq b_o = \sqrt{1 - \|T_2^H(M^+)_\beta e_y^o\|^2} (4.9)$$

The above test yields a yes or no answer. If the test fails, then the model is invalidated either due to overly restricted levels of noise and/or disturbance and/or insufficiently rich uncertainty LFT structure. Suppose the above constant matrix test is passed. For the existence of a model validating set, ξ must also satisfy the $G - \Delta$ feedback conditions

$$\xi = \Delta \eta (4.10)$$

$$\eta = G_{11}\xi + G_{12}\beta + G_{13}r (4.11)$$

Since η can be readily computed from Eqn. (4.11) for a given ξ and β , Eqns. (4.8) and (4.11) are grouped as shown:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \eta \\ \xi \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \eta_o \\ \xi_o \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} G_{11} & G_{12} \\ I_{n_\xi} & 0_{n_\xi \times n_\beta} \end{bmatrix} \Omega \begin{bmatrix} \phi \\ \psi \end{bmatrix} (4.12)$$

where $\eta_o = [G_{11} \ G_{12}] \begin{bmatrix} \xi_o \\ \beta_o \end{bmatrix} + G_{13}r$.

Eqn. (4.12) characterizes the set of all (ξ, η) vectors that produce zero output error. Of course, this set may be further constrained by the uncertainty structure given by Eqn. (4.10). Consider a general uncertainty structure, which includes repeated scalar blocks and/or real scalar blocks. The following result [14] gives the parameterization of the model validating sets.

Theorem 4.1:

(a) Suppose the constant matrix tests are satisfied. Then a model validating set exists with $\Delta_i = \delta_i I_{n_i}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$, $\delta_i \in F_i$ if and only if there exists ψ , and ϕ with $\|\phi\| \leq b_0$ such that the (ξ, η) pair parameterized by ϕ and ψ as given in Eqn. (4.12) is D-realizable and

$$\text{for each } i = 1, 2, \dots, m \\ \text{either } \xi_i = 0 \text{ or } \text{dist}^{(F_i)}(\xi_i, \eta_i) = 0 \quad (4.13)$$

where ξ_i and η_i are appropriately partitioned vectors given by Eqn. (4.12).

(b) Furthermore, if a model validating set exists, then all such sets are given by

$$D_{\phi\psi} W = \{\Delta \in D : \Delta = \Delta_B W, \bar{\sigma}(\Delta_B) \leq 1\} \quad (4.14)$$

where $\psi \in C^{n_w}$, $\|\phi\| \leq b_0$, $W = \text{diag}[\omega_1 I_{n_1}, \omega_2 I_{n_2}, \dots, \omega_m I_{n_m}]$ is any diagonal complex matrix whose diagonal elements satisfy

$$|\omega_i| \geq \frac{\|\xi_i\|}{\|\eta_i\|}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, \tau \quad (4.15)$$

and the (ξ, η) pair parameterized by ϕ and ψ as given in Eqn. (4.12) is D-realizable and satisfies condition (4.13).

4.3 Uncertainty Bound Optimization

Suppose to improve a model, parameter identification using all available information is performed. In principle, after this adjustment, there is no reason to model this parameter as bounded but unknown. In practice, however, this adjustment may not work perfectly since everything else must be assumed "perfectly" known, and the results depend largely on the choice of parameter set.

Alternately, lower and upper bounds are specified to reflect unknown but constant parameters. We propose solving for the smallest non-parametric uncertainties subject to allowance in exogenous disturbance/noise and parametric uncertainties. Justifications: (i) a joint numerical optimization of parametric and non-parametric uncertainties is difficult to justify on physical grounds; and (ii) (physical) parameters are in general less uncertain than non-parametric uncertainties (typically unmodeled dynamics). Given a set of uncertainty weights, W , we seek a smallest x such that $D_{(xW)}$ is a model validating set. The following optimization problem is considered.

A Smallest Model Validating Uncertainty Set Algorithm:

$$\text{Min } x \quad (4.16) \\ \psi, \phi, \delta_1, \dots, \delta_r, \xi$$

subject to the constraints

$$\delta_i \in F_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, r \quad (4.17)$$

$$\xi_i = \delta_i \eta_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, r \quad (4.18)$$

$$|\delta_i|^2 - x^2 |\omega_i|^2 \leq 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, r \quad (4.19)$$

$$|\xi_i|^2 - x^2 |\omega_i|^2 \|\eta_i\|^2 \leq 0, \quad i = r+1, \dots, \tau \quad (4.20)$$

$$x \geq 0 \quad (4.21)$$

$$\|\phi\| \leq b_0 \quad (4.22)$$

where ξ_i and η_i are parameterized by Eqns. (4.12).

In summary, given input and output experimental data and a nominal plant model with an LFT uncertainty structure, constant matrix tests for the existence of a model validating uncertainty set are given. All unknown but bounded exogenous disturbances are assumed to occur as additive measurement noise and as disturbances to the plant. Under mild conditions, these constant matrix tests are necessary and sufficient for the existence of model validating uncertainty sets for the given LFT uncertainty structure. With the satisfaction of these tests, a parameterization of all model-validating sets of plant models is possible and can be used as a basis for uncertainty tradeoffs among different model validating uncertainty models all having a specific LFT uncertainty structure.

5. Concluding Remarks

This paper has presented three modeling methods that can be used in combination or separately for application to robust and LPV control system analysis and design problems. These methods include: (1) a multivariate polynomial modeling method based on orthogonal function modeling that can be used in developing an LPV model of the system; (2) a parametric uncertainty modeling method to compute a low-order LFT model based on the LPV model of the system; and (3) an uncertainty bound identification method that can be used to obtain a validated mixed uncertainty model based on the parametric LFT model and assuming an uncertainty structure to characterize unmodeled system dynamics. When the three methods are combined, a validated mixed uncertainty model can be obtained for nonlinear parameter-dependent systems involving both parametric and non-parametric uncertainties.

The uncertainty modeling methods presented in this paper provide a computer-aided uncertainty modeling capability for a broad range of difficult practical problems. An example uncertainty modeling problem for an F-16 aircraft is given in Ref. [15]. Software has been developed for the multivariate polynomial modeling method described in Section 2.1, and is under development for the parametric LFT computation method of Section 3 and the uncertainty bound identification method presented in Section 4.

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